

ROADMAP

Rethinking of antimicrobial decision-systems in the management of animal production

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ROADMAP Guidelines for Recruitment of Stakeholders

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About the ROADMAP research project

The overall aim of ROADMAP is to **foster transitions towards prudent use of antimicrobials (AMs) in animal production in different contexts to manage antimicrobial resistance (AMR). Prudent antimicrobial use (AMU) will be achieved by enhancing antimicrobial decision-systems along the food and drug supply chains.** ROADMAP will focus on supporting animal health and welfare through prevention and health promotion actions.

AMR is recognized as a significant threat to global public health and food security. Overuse and improper use of AMs in many parts of the world contribute to the emergence and spread of AMR. Although human and animal health require AMs, it has been estimated that two thirds of the future AMU growth worldwide will be in animal production. Improving the management of AMU in farm animals is therefore a critical component of dealing with AMR and optimizing production in the livestock sector. Nevertheless, the variety of contexts of AMU in the livestock sector is a major challenge to managing AMR. **There is no “one-size-fits-all” solution to improve AMU and strategies must be contextually developed** (for instance, strategies used in the Danish pig industry are difficult to adapt and adopt in the French free-range poultry farming). Successful solutions must be combined and tailored to the production systems and the social and economic context in which they operate.

ROADMAP will meet three general objectives, in line with the EU AMR Action plan:

- i) Rethink AM decision-systems and animal health management;
- ii) Develop options for encouraging prudent AMU in animal production;
- iii) Engage all actors in the food and drug supply chains in fostering a more prudent use of AMs.

Project consortium

Part. N°	Participant organisation name (acronym)	Country
1	Institut National de Recherche pour l'Agriculture, l'Alimentation et l'Environnement (INRAE) **	France
2	Association de coordination technique agricole (ACTA) ***	France
3	Centre de coopération internationale en recherche agronomique pour le développement (CIRAD) **	France
4	University of Liverpool (ULIV) *	United Kingdom
5	Cardiff University (CU) *	United Kingdom
6	James Hutton Institute (HUT) **	United Kingdom
7	Alma Mater Studiorum - Università di Bologna (UNIBO) *	Italy
8	Aarhus Universitet (AU) *	Denmark
9	Eigen Vermogen van het Instituut voor Landbouw en Visserijonderzoek (EV-ILVO) **	Belgium
10	Research Institute of Organic Agriculture (FiBL) **	Switzerland
11	Stichting Wageningen Research (WR) *	Netherlands
12	Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (SLU) *	Sweden
13	Southern Agriculture and Horticulture Organization (ZLTO) ***	Netherlands
14	European Forum of Farm Animal Breeders (EFFAB) ****	Netherlands
15	Fundacion Empresa Universidad Gallega (FEUGA) ****	Spain
16	Dierengezondheidszorg Vlaanderen (DGZ) ***	Belgium
17	INRAE Transfert (IT) ****	France

* *Universities/veterinary schools*

** *Research institutes specialized in both fundamental and applied agricultural and veterinary sciences*

*** *Public and private advisory services Organisations*

**** *Knowledge transfer and Innovation organisations*

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List of acronyms and abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
ACTA	Association de Coordination Technique Agricole
AMR	Antimicrobial Resistance
AMs	Antimicrobials
AMU	Antimicrobial use
ANIS-EMA	AU Epidemiology and Management research unit
AU	Aarhus Universitet
AU-ANIS	AU Department of Animal Science
CA	Consortium Agreement
CIRAD	Centre de cooperation internationale en recherche agronomique pour le développement
CLs	County leaders
COGECA	General Committee for Agricultural Cooperation in the European Union
COPA	Committee of Professional Agricultural Organisations
CU	Cardiff University
D	Deliverable
DoA	Description of Action
DGZ	Dierengezondheidszorg Vlaanderen VZW
DISTAL	Department of Agricultural and Food Science
DLS	Department of Livestock Sciences
DMP	Data Management Plan
EAAP	European Federation of Animal Science
EC	European Commission
EFFAB	European Forum of Farm Animal Breeders
EIP-AGRI	The Agricultural European Innovation Partnership
EU	European Union
EV-ILVO	Eigen vermogen van het instituut voor landbouw en visserijonderzoek
ExCom	Executive Committee
FABRE-TP	Farm Animal Breeding and Reproduction Technology Platform
FEUGA	Fundacion empresa Universidad Gallega
FiBL	Forschungsinstitut für biologischen landbau stiftung
FSL	Food Safety Lab
FVE	Federation of Veterinarians of Europe
HUT	The James Hutton Institute
ICOH	International Conference on One Health
INRA	Institut national de la recherche agronomique
IPR	Intellectual property rights
IPUDC	Intellectual Property Use and Dissemination Committee

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IT	INRAE Transfert
ITAs	Technical Agricultural Institutes
MAA	Multi Actor Approach
MS	Milestone
NGOs	Non-governmental organisations
ODP	Outreach & Dissemination Plan
PEDR	Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Results
RSCs	Regional Stakeholder Communities
SAB	Stakeholder advisory board
SLU	Sveriges Lantbruksuniversitet
UEVP	Union of European Veterinary Practitioners
ULIV	The University of Liverpool
UNIBO	Alma Mater Studiorum – Università di Bologna
WBVR	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
WLR	Wageningen UR Livestock Research
WOHC	World One Health Congress
WP	Work Package
WPLs	Work Package Leaders
WR	Stichting Wageningen Research
WVAC	World Veterinary Association Congress
ZLTO	Zuidelijke land- en tuinbouworganisatie vereniging

1 Summary

ROADMAP is a multi-actor approach (MAA) research project, which means that project partners must have complementary types of knowledge from research and practice. This document presents a protocol for the creation of a stakeholder’s community, how they will be engaged and what kind of stakeholder’s knowledge is needed to reach the goals set, where and when those stakeholders are going to be involved.

This deliverable will be updated during the project life with a mid-term report, which shows the results achieved.

2 Introduction

Task T7.1 entitled “Stakeholders community creation and management” is conducted as part of WP7 “Strategic communication, dissemination & exploitation”. Stakeholders community creation and management is described in the ROADMAP Grant Agreement through different actions.

D7.1. presents the methodological basis for the creation of the Stakeholders community. It is an easy-to-use guidelines document for the recruitment of stakeholders and devoted to the partners will be issued. One partner per ROADMAP country will be in charge of engaging the stakeholders at regional/national level. A specific section of the project website gives visibility to the ROADMAP stakeholders community.

A Stakeholder Advisory Board will also be created and its members will be invited to the project annual meetings to be informed sufficiently about the project progress and be able to provide feedback. In order to increase the interaction between the project partners and the Stakeholders, different methods of engagement such as round table discussions, problem tree analysis, speed networking activities.... will be organised during these meetings.

3 The stakeholder community

The protocol regarding the creation of ROADMAP’s Stakeholders Community will answer the 5 basic questions about **why** this protocol is needed, **which** actors will be involved, **how** they will be involved, **what** kind of knowledge is needed to reach the objectives set on each WP and the overall objective of ROADMAP project, **where** the interactions with stakeholders will take place and **when** these interactions will be developed.

3.1 WHY?

To assess the main objectives set on the Grant Agreement it is compulsory to establish a protocol that guide all actors involved on ROADMAP.

The main objectives of this **ROADMAP Regional Stakeholder Community (RSC)** are:

- To improve knowledge exchange between scientists, and stakeholders

- To co-create new knowledge
- To put into practice research results

3.2 WHO?

ROADMAP fully meets the multi-actor approach, since a wide diversity of actors (as partners, beneficiaries and third parties) are already members of the project, including non-academic partners that have been integrated from the beginning within the consortium. However, ROADMAP members will also work actively with animal health professionals and stakeholders that are not officially part of the consortium.

ROADMAP will develop innovative participatory methods for co-working throughout the project and set up regional communities.

Stakeholders that are going to be part of the RSC include farmers’ and producers’ organizations; animal production advisors; veterinary practices and professional organizations; breeding, feeding and pharmaceutical companies; retailers and processors; national public authorities.

To involve and concretely engage this range of stakeholders, ROADMAP will create RSCs at national level in all the countries where ROADMAP undertakes research activities. Each RSC will be composed of a balanced representation of these key actors in designated countries and will facilitate dialogue and discussion.

REGIONAL STAKEHOLDERS COMMUNITIES (RSCs)

Figure 1 Regional stakeholders community (RSC)

RSCs will be composed by:

- **Work Package leaders (WPLs):** They will provide the technical contribution to the project, and participate in the RSCs of their regions, helping Country leaders to select and supervise the activities carry out by Country Leaders.
- **Country Leaders (CLs):** country leaders will identify and engage with stakeholders with the support of WPs 1-6 leaders. They will organize workshops/roundtables (additional to those planned in WPs 1-6) with the intention of covering potential gaps (for instance in terms of stakeholders profiles not sufficiently covered, knowledge gaps, and mainly regions not covered). These activities included in WP7 and led by country leaders will complement to the work planned in WPs 1-6, in which the tasks must be integrated. They will provide the geographical contribution to the project. The CLs may involve some other members of the project in the RSCs when relevant.
- **Stakeholders.** They will guarantee the link with the large community of end-users. Following the instruction of the CLs, they will propose ideas, share their knowledge and experiences in order to develop the activities of the community and to achieve its objectives.

Figure 2 RSCs selection and composition

3.2.1 Stakeholder's identification

The WPLs (technical contribution) and CLs (national contribution) will propose and select the stakeholders to be involved in the RSCs of their country. They will keep in mind the specificities of the country and the topics and areas of expertise selected. Besides a minimum common basis has to be observed, the RSCs

has to be composed of different categories of stakeholders in order to guarantee a balanced composition from different perspectives (including gender and age aspects) and complementary types of knowledge:

Table 1: Description of the RSCs stakeholder categories

	CATEGORY	DESCRIPTION
1.	Practitioners (animal health professionals):	people who are expected to implement the solutions proposed in field: farmers, veterinarians, technical advisors and farmer’s organizations.
2.	Private partners:	small and medium enterprises (SME's) linked to the activity, like breeding and feeding industries, pharmaceutical companies, retailers and processors.
3.	Multipliers:	sector and professional associations, NGO’s, EIP-AGRI operational groups from the specific country, regional or national agricultural project partners and networks and other public or private initiatives relevant for the agricultural sector.
4.	Researchers:	researcher groups from universities or technological centres which offer knowledge about agricultural. They have to be able to share their experience and knowledge within the RSCs.
5.	Policy-makers and administration:	public authorities from different policy areas who can foster new politics, regulations or means to empower the sector.

People invited to join the RSCs in each one of these categories must have a specific profile in order to play adequately their role as a member of the community. The general profile expected is dynamic people with decision making skills who works on organizations with important links in the sector. The most relevant **profile characteristics desired from the RSCs stakeholders are:**

Table 2: Characteristics from the RSCs stakeholder categories

	CATEGORY	SPECIFIC PROFILES
1.	Practitioners (animal health professionals):	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Model/Reference for the rest of practitioners · Important background and practical experience
2.	Private partners:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Model/Reference for the rest of stakeholders · Important background and practical experience
3.	Multipliers:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Having a wide network and adequate communication tools to disseminate to the target audience
4.	Researchers:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Lines of research or projects focused on AMU and AMR, agriculture, livestock and other related fields of knowledge. · Experience in working with farmers and other practitioners.
5.	Policy-makers and administration:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Being able to assess the feasibility (concerning legal framework) of the alternatives and strategies identified.

CLs will try to involve a **core group of representatives for each category and to include a majority of practitioners** (a third of stakeholders is recommended). WPLs will help them to cover **potential gaps** (for instance in terms of stakeholders profiles not sufficiently covered, knowledge gaps, and mainly regions not covered).

Each WPLs and CLs **are free to select the stakeholders in the most convenient way**. CLs know best the national situation and how to approach their target group. Most of the regions will have already a list of stakeholders. Contact all of these people in order to know their interest is recommended through a meeting, by telephone or by e-mail (see annex 1 for an example). However, it is expected that even if an email might be a good first step to introduce the project and the idea of the RSCs, subsequently more direct communication will be needed. If possible, presenting ROADMAP project in a national event where most of the stakeholders participate like breeding shows, trade fairs, workshops or conferences hosted by local umbrella organisations or maybe at a TV program on livestock would certainly increase the awareness to the project and would create more attention. Connections with national and/or regional agricultural journalists would increase the efficiency of profile raising events.

Table 3: Table for selection of individuals to participate in RSCs

Criteria	Written comments
Interest	
Availability/Commitment	
Relevance	
Appropriateness	
Representativeness	
Willingness	

Other aspects should be take into account when categorising stakeholders for a better classification and final report.

Table 4: Table for factor identification

Factor	Written comments
Gender	
Age	
Country/Region	

We can classify stakeholders by their level of expertise but also by their level of involvement, this segmentation should be taken into account to help the development of the D7.5 Mid-term report on stakeholder consultations to be publish at the middle of the project which aims to report about the stakeholder meeting minutes, survey results, notes...to measure the impact achieved by this period.

3.2.1.1 By type of expertise:

Operational Level: animal health professionals

It will be composed by animal health professionals at farm level like farmers, veterinarians, technical advisor & farmer’s organizations. This is a provisional list of potential members of this level already proposed by partners but this list will be expanded during the project lifetime with the technical contribution of the WPLs and the regional view of the CLs.

Strategic level: industries and public authorities

This level will be composed by actor intervening in food/drug supply chains as pharmaceutical companies, breeding and feeding industries, retailers & processors or policy makers. As with the operational level this list of potential members is the previous one proposed by partners but this list will be expanded during the project lifetime with the technical contribution of the WPLs and the regional view of the CLs.

3.2.1.2 *By level of implication:*

Among the stakeholder's community are two degrees of implication.

- **Level 1** includes those **actively involved**. They participate at some workshops, interact within other stakeholders and make contributions to the stakeholder's platform.
- **Level 2** is constituted by the **final users of the project results**. Key stakeholders can be considered as a subgroup of stakeholders who might be seriously impacted by the fulfilment of the project objectives. Most animal health professional will be impacted with the activities of ROADMAP even if there is no direct contact with ROADMAP partners or activities by the implementation of AMU solutions propose on their agri-food activities.

3.3 HOW?

To know how stakeholders will be involved and engaged we link at the end of the deliverable a set of templates related with the nature of the tasks.

Regarding the relationship among RSC's members, the CLs will work closely with the WPLs to ensure that ROADMAP meets its objectives. For its part, the CLs will be the reliable person for the stakeholders and the main link between them and the rest of the partners.

WPLs responsibilities

- Help identifying stakeholders.
- Contribute to the area of expertise or topics for the RSCs.
- Collaborate in summarizing the information and results of the RSCs workshops and meetings when relevant to their WP.

CLs responsibilities

- Create the RSCs in their region.
- To support the RSCs members.
- To monitor the RSCs activity and guarantee compliance with the objectives.
- To guarantee the effective internal communication among the members of the network.

Stakeholders responsibilities

- To actively participate in the RSCs meetings
- To openly share their experience and knowledge within the network.
- To propose improvements for the RSCs activities
- To be involved and engaged in the development of the RSCs activities (see below for the different possible types of involvement and engagement)

3.3.1 Stakeholder’s Involvement

The final procedure followed will be reported to FEUGA, the leader of the creation and coordination of RSCs and responsible partner of this deliverable.

Table 5: Table for involvement levels

INVOLVEMENT LEVELS				
1. INFORM	2. LISTEN	3. CONSULT	4. INVOLVE	5. COLLABORATE
One-way communication: project to stakeholder, there is no invitation to reply	One-way communication: stakeholder to project	Two-way limited: project asks questions and stakeholders answers	Two-way or multiway engagement, learning on all sides, but acting independent way	Two way joint learning, decision making and actions

Table 6: Table for methods of engagement

METHODS OF ENGAGEMENT				
INFORM	LISTEN	CONSULT	INVOLVE	COLLABORATE
Bulletins and letters	Media and internet tracking	Consultations	Multistakeholder forums	Joint projects
Brochures	Letters/emails	Focus group/workshops	Advisory panels	Joint ventures
Reports and websites/social media	Second hand reports from other stakeholders via interviews	Meeting with selected stakeholders/public meetings	Participatory decision-making processes/ focus group	Partnerships
Speeches, conference and public presentation	Social media	Social media	Consensus building processes	Multistakeholder initiatives
			Online engagement tools	Online collaborative platforms

3.3.1.1 Invitation to participate in the RSCs

The identification of candidate members for each RSCs will be in two steps:

- a) Creation of a preliminary list of potential members for the RSCs, taking into consideration the recommendations of the WPLs (technical contribution) and CLs (regional contribution).
- b) Invitation to Participate in a RSCs:

- Initial contact with candidate members of the RSCs will be made by the partner leading the WPs and CLs. Candidate members will be provided with the Information Sheet about ROADMAP and the roles of the members of the RSCs. A draft of the Information Sheet for RSCs is provided in Annex 2;
- The official letter of invitation will be sent by the Project Coordinator. A draft of the letter of invitation to be part of the RSCs is provided in Annex 1. This include a content to fulfil depending if the stakeholder is going to participate on case studies.

3.3.2 Stakeholder’s engagement

One of the most relevant challenges of ROADMAP project is to involve the stakeholders in the RSC’s activities, achieving their real engagement with the objectives of the network. Engaged work will be done by CLs on their workshops, trainings... and by communicating and disseminating the results through specific channels (see 7.3 PEDR).

In addition, the CLs will have different means to keep the RSCs members informed: email, phone, social media... The selected methods of communication for ROADMAP stakeholder’s community are an online repository managed by FEUGA and Facebook groups for sharing interesting information managed by EFFAB.

Roadmap stakeholders structure

The ROADMAP stakeholders are grouped under two categories in ROADMAP. International Stakeholders’ Platform (SP) and Regional Stakeholder Communities (RSCs).

Figure 3 Structure of ROADMAP Stakeholders

The Stakeholder’s Platform is an international community which consists of Operational and Strategic Committees which feed into the Stakeholder Advisory Board (SAB). The Operational Committee comprises of farmers, veterinarians, technical advisors and farmers’ organisations and the Strategic Committee comprises of pharmaceutical companies, breeding & feeding industries, retailers & processors, policy makers. The members of the Stakeholder Advisory Board (SAB) are selected from the representatives of different actors.

Regional Stakeholder Communities (RSCs) represent the national stakeholders in partner countries which are initiated and managed by the Country leaders (CLs) or Case-Study Leaders (CSs) and have member of the Living labs. Work Package Leaders (WPLs) will also have a technical contribution by feeding the RSCs with inputs and results from ROADMAP’s research activities.

The common contact point for both the international and the national Stakeholder Community is the Digital Stakeholder Platform which facilitates knowledge exchange and dissemination of ROADMAP results, this will include a repository and link to Facebook groups (Figure 4).

Figure 4 ROADMAP Stakeholders’ Community (Facebook)

The Stakeholders’ Repository will be an online space inside the ROADMAP official website where an interactive georeferenced map will show the regions covered by the project, and the different stakeholders engaged.

Stakeholders can register themselves directly on the form allocated on the platform, and they should have access to open information about the interaction with the community. Some different access levels of users will be created, in order to give privilege access to key stakeholders, this option will be done by FEUGA once establish with the rest of the consortium the levels of confidentiality.

These members will be allowed to comment documents, surveys... It is quite important to add a double consent in the registration form to appear on the stakeholder’s repository in order to comply with the GDPR.

It will also contain a notification system to alert by email to stakeholders when a document or event is publishing or updated. A calendar of events and meeting will be created, and related initiatives will be spread (operational groups, EIP-AGRI events).

Figure 5 Stakeholder’s repository (BETA VERSION)

3.4 WHERE?

Fieldwork will be developed in 10 countries and it will feed the national case-studies: France; Belgium; Switzerland; Netherlands; Italy; Sweden; UK; Denmark; Vietnam; Mozambique. They have been chosen to highlight different systemic variables and contexts and enable an in-depth understanding of different regions of Europe and worldwide.

The fieldworks will cover 4 animal production systems: poultry, pig, beef and dairy cattle.

ROADMAP CASE STUDIES MAP

Figure 6 Case studies by country and animal production

3.5 WHEN?

It is important to define when the interactions will have place depending on the goal for each WP. After asking the WPLs we can offer an initial calendar of actions that will be uploaded with the project lifetime. In first place we introduce a schedule of the intended actions plan between WPLs and CLs with the stakeholders selected and in second hand we focus on the relation between WPLs (technical contribution) and CLs (regional contribution), to measure the impact achieved.

WP7 activities on stakeholder's involvement and engagement will closely interact with other relevant activities of the project, in particular those based on participative approaches. The other WPs whose core-methodology is based on such participative approaches are WP3 and 4 for the Living Labs, and WP6 for the Impact and Transition Pathways Assessment. See below a list of activities which will highly rely on stakeholder engagement and feed the RSCs.

Table 7: Calendar

WP	LINK TASKS	INVOLVED PARTNERS	LINK WP
WP3. Co-building levers and incentives	T3.1: Building & sharing a common theoretical and methodological framework for setting-up Living Labs	WPL	WPs
	M1-12 Partners development of guidelines for living labs M1-12		
	T3.2: Identifying critical points for change and indicators	All CS involved	WP1,2,4
	M7-18 Joint International meeting (to identify stakeholder)		
	M7-18 Living labs selection of stakeholders (farmers, vets and others)		
	T3.3: Participatory design of integrative strategies from industry to farms	All CS involved	WP1,4
	M13-27 3 co-design meetings (industrial and business stakeholders)		
	T3.4: Participatory design of integrative strategies for animal health management	All CS involved	WP2,4
M13-27 Living labs with animal health professionals (farmers, vets and advisors)			
WP4. Implementing and further development of strategies to reduce AMU	T4.1 Building and sharing a joint theoretical and methodological framework for implementing Living labs and co-learning events	WPL	All WPs
	M18. Webinar on how to implement living labs. All partners		
	Exchange WP3 and WP4 for guideline of living labs		
	T4.2 Compilation of strategies to reduce AMU across Europe and beyond	ZLTO	WP3
	Collection of measures desk research and expert interviews M7-24		
	T4.3 Implementing selected solutions	All CS involved	WP3,5,6,7
	M21. 1 st meeting to describe strategy to implement selected solutions (each partner at regional level). Individual stakeholders to collect data about costs, animal health and AMU.		
	M29. 2 nd meeting to implement the strategy (each partner at regional level). Individual stakeholders to collect data about costs, animal health and AMU.		
	M37. 3 rd meeting to evaluate the process and impact (each partner at regional level). Individual stakeholders to collect data about costs, animal health and AMU.		
	T4.4 Exchange and co-learning	All CS involved	WP3,7
M30. International joint reflective workshop in the Netherlands organize by ZLTO. Partners from the different Living labs.			
M42. International joint reflective workshop in Switzerland organize by FiBL. Partners from the different Living labs.			

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WP6. Creating Impact from what we have learned

T6.1 Development of an adapted impact assessment methodology and review of AMR impact assessment studies	WPLs	All WPs
M1-18 Adaptation ImpresS method		
T6.2 Identification of stakeholders desired impact	All CS involved	WP1,2,5
M7-24. Trainings on impact assessment methodology will be performed through participative workshops to identify stakeholder's behaviours and impact expectations. Project partners and stakeholders (animal health professionals)		
T6.3 Ex-ante impact assessment	All CS involved	WP3,4,5
M13-M36. Stakeholder workshops to co-construct the relevant impact pathway		
T6.4 Transversal impact assessment and recommendations for transition pathways towards prudent AMU	All CS involved	WP5
M 45. Transversal analysis performed between 2 case studies (ImpresS Method)		

WP7. Strategic communication, dissemination & exploitation

T7.1 Stakeholders community creation and management	EFFAB, ACTA, CIRAD, HUT, UNIBO, EV-ILVO, SLU, ZLTO, DGZ	WP1 to WP6
M1-M48 Creation of the Stakeholder platform		
M1-M48 Manage information, documents uploaded and georeferencial map		
M1-M48 Manage the community creation and look forward the image of the community to avoid potential gaps (for instance in terms of stakeholders profiles not sufficiently covered, knowledge gaps, and mainly regions not covered) and ask CLs to develop actions needed to reach the community objective.		
T7.2. Communication activities	INRA/ FEUGA	WP1 to WP6
Beginning of the project. Profile raising act. International stakeholders (Annual meeting FVE or VEV, CPOA-COCEGA, ICOH...)		
6 th November Fitter Livestock Farming workshop (ROADMAP is presented)		
Mid-term/ final Project. Networking drinks and lunch meet up. Influential stakeholder's representatives (umbrella organizations) and pharma companies, policy makers and media representatives.		
T7.3. Dissemination of project results	All partners	WP1 to WP6
International scientific conference like WVAC. Researchers		
Final conference. All stakeholders		
T7.4 ROADMAP Training	INRA, FiBL, ZLTO, EFFAB	WP1 to WP6
M7-48. Co-learning exchange events (Switzerland, France, Denmark and Italy) Farmers, vets and advisory services		

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M7-48. Mini webinar series. Industrial stakeholders (breeding/feeding/ Pharmaceuticals/ farm technologies...)

3.6 EVALUATION AND MONITORING

WPLs and CLs will have several meetings in order to monitor ROADMAP activities and to avoid the potential gaps mentioned before (for instance in terms of stakeholders profiles not sufficiently covered, knowledge gaps, and mainly regions not covered). There will be at least ten meetings according to the schedule proposed: some of them will be face-to-face meetings for preparing the work at regional level; and others will be virtual meetings to monitor the activity. FEUGA will be able to adapt this schedule based on the progress of the project, the RSCs activities or other relevant reasons. Changes will be informed and justified to INRA (as coordinator of ROADMAP project) and to FEUGA (as responsible partner of the RSCs guidelines).

Table 8: Schedule of WPLs & CLs meetings

N.	DATE	DESCRIPTION	TYPE OF MEETING
1	KOM June 2019	Validation of the Country Leaders responsible list	Face-to-face
2	Extra Annual meeting to confirm February 2020 (M9)	Design of framework for proceeding interventions	Face-to-face
3	June 2020 Annual meeting (M13)	Preparation of the RSCs workshops	Face-to-face
4	June 2021 Annual meeting (M25)	Preparation of the RSCs workshops: analysis and conclusions	Face-to-face
5	June 2022 annual meeting (M37)	Preparation of the third workshops of RSCs	Face-to-face
6	May 2023 Final annual meeting (M48)	Preparation of the final workshops of RSCs: collection of ideas for the sustainability plan for ROADMAP, identification of potential framework events to include the ROADMAP final conference.	Face-to-face

Face-to-face meetings will be coupled with the Consortium General Assembly's and also emails between CLs and WPLs would be the tool used for monitoring the RSCs, in particular WP7, to deal with any kind of issues.

4 Stakeholder Advisory Board

To strength durable links with a large Stakeholders Community during and after the end of the project, international Stakeholder Advisory Board members (SAB) will be created to provide recommendations to the Executive Committee (see MS35 for more details). It will be used for feedback and input on the project results and outcomes, to advise on the dissemination, communication and exploitation strategies. The SAB will also be consulted regarding RSCs management and engagement.

The SAB will be composed of a dozen of international stakeholders’ representatives selected amongst the main European/international organisations representing the different areas and types of stakeholders concerned by ROADMAP’s activities: farmers, veterinarians, upstream and downstream industries, consumers, policy-makers and relevant experts from other project and/or funding bodies.

SAB members will meet the ROADMAP ExCom once a year, during the ROADMAP General Assembly by video conferencing or physically over, will be informed and consulted on a regular basis and will attend the project meetings whenever necessary. This group will be managed by EFFAB.

List of experts who have already accepted to join the SAB as it is showed on DoA. We will complete it by adding representatives from all categories of stakeholders.

Table 9: Stakeholder Advisory Board members

Type	Organisation
Veterinarians	Union of European Veterinary Practitioners
Medical, veterinary and environmental community	One Health EJP
Animal Health International Consortium	STAR-IDAZ
Animal Health World Organization	OIE
Animal Breeders Federation	ADT
Animal Science Society	BSAS

Figure 7 Roadmap Stakeholder Platform

5 METHODOLOGY

This section explains the methodology on how representativeness, selection transparency and the steps taken to avoid selection, ascertainment bias and conflict of interest.

We can focus on the different levels of groups involved to include this aspects:

5.1 SAB

The selection was made attending the criteria of members of the value chain with European or international representativeness. We create a first list of interesting organizations from the proposal stage, that has been worked with EXCOM partners to end with of an ideal list of institutions to contact. Finally, SAB group was created after the confirmation of some of this contacted organizations and they send a representative to join our project monitoring and advisory group. They all have signed a Letter of intention and a confidentiality agreement.

Table 10: Final list SAB members

Name	Organisation	Job description	Group
Arnoud Bouxin	European Manufacturers' Federation (FEFAC)	Feed Deputy General Secretary	Feed
Roxane Feller	AnimalhealthEurope	Secretary General	Animal Health
David John		Senior Policy Technical Manager	
Hans-Peter Schons	FESSAS Fédération Européenne pour la Santé Animale et la Sécurité Sanitaire / German Animal Breeders Federation (ADT)	Vice-President Delegate	Animal Health and Health Security
Jan Vaarten	FVE (retired) and HealthyLivestock	Executive Director	Vets
Elisabeth Erlacher-Vindel	OIE	OIE focal point on tripartite (FAO/OIE/WHO) activities on AMR	Animal Health/Policy maker
Taylor Gabourie		AMR Communications Officer	
Hein Imberechts	One Health EJP and Sciensano	Scientific Coordinator of the One Health EJP and Scientific Support Advisor & Biosafety Officer at Sciensano	Animal Health
Koen Vervoort	European Network of Living Labs (ENOLL)	Network Builder	Civic & Social Organization

Alex Morrow	STAR-IDAZ and DEFRA	Star-Idaz and Evidence Lead, Animal Health and Welfare at DEFRA	Coordinator International	Animal Health
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They have already participated at two general assemblies on June 2020 and April 2021 attending some of the workshops and work package presentations and giving their advice and proposals.

5.2 Regional communities

The members of the regional communities organised at regional level are involved by several methods.

Roadmap regional communities will have available some dedicated areas within the Roadmap website, one public and open to every stakeholder interested on the project progress and others private addressed to list of stakeholders involved at living labs closing groups. For instance, Belgium case, has a public page where information regarding the project progress is explained in Dutch, and also two private pages, one for calves and cattle and another for pigs, addressed to the members of each living lab with private information about minutes, presentations and other interesting information.

With an open participation through the Roadmap communication channels: website, social networks to a close participation formed by participants include at:

5.2.1 Case study level

In the various case study, interviews with vets and farmers are conducted within the framework of WP2. In many cases, this work is still ongoing. The participants are selected according to the research questions that drive this WP and through the method of snow-ball sampling and the principle of data saturation: representativeness is achieved when variation amongst certain criteria that matters for the research is obtained. The main criteria are age, gender, sectors, and farming systems (for farmers) and business models (for vets). The selection also follows GDPR rules to ensure data confidentiality and avoid conflict of interests

5.2.2 Living labs level

Table 11: Final list Living labs with coordinators and stakeholder representing

Living Lab	Coordinators and facilitators	Stakeholders representing
Belgian pigs	Erwin	Different farmer Unions, veterinary practioners, Animal Health Care Services, Federal agency of the Safety of the Foodchain, Federal Agency for medicines and health products, Expertise Center for Antimicrobiolal Usage and Resistance, Academical Research centers and universities, farmaceutical companies, Centre for Agro-and fisheries marketing, National Federation of slaughterhouses, cutting plants and wholesalers, retailers, National feed assocoation, feed and nutrition companies, Sector guide organisations for primary production, Agricultural research, innovation and information centers, Department of Agriculture and Fisheries, Belgian Veal Calve Assocoation
Belgian veal	Wauters, ILVO Stefaan Ribbens, DGZ	

Danish pigs	Hanne Kongsted, ICROFS Line Kollerup, AU Merete Studnitz, ICROFS	Producers, extension services, vets, industry (R&D, extension, export consultant), slaughterhouses, researcher, retailer
Danish dairy (cows and calves)	Line Kollerup, AU Mette Vaarst, AU	Veterinary practice and advisory service, university education of vets and ag scientists, The Danish Vet. Society, 3 companies involved in the dairy or calf sectors (a dairy company with conventional and organic milk, a meat trading company and a company for calf feed and equipment), The Agricultural Advisory Service Centre, SEGES, under the Danish Agricultural Agency (the Danish farming sector's organization)
Dutch poultry (turkeys)	Fleur Hoorweg, WR Annick Spaans, ZLTO Heleen Prinsen, ZLTO Anne Marie Rebel, WR	Veterinary practice, Animal Health service, 3 farmers board members of the branche organisation (AVINED), branch organisation (AVINED), Dutch farmers organization, Feed organization, Wageningen University and research.
French poultry & pigs	Catherine Belloc, ONIRIS Nantes Mathilde Paul, ENVT Christian Ducrot, INRAE,	French Ministry of Agriculture, Veterinary practitioners (pig and poultry sectors), Interprofessional councils (INAPORC for pig and ANVOL for poultry), development institutes (IFIP for pig and ITAVI for poultry)
French dairy	Eleonore Pommier, Idele Manon Fuselier, Idele Mathilde Paul, ENVT Marlene Guiadeur, Idele Aurore D. Wache, Idele	(LL not started yet, so here are the stakeholders we would like to invite): farmers, veterinarians, milk industries, federation of health protection groups, French livestock advisors
Italian poultry	Massimo Canali, UNIBO Frederique Pascali, UNIBO Caetano Luiz Beber, UNIBO	French Ministry of Agriculture, Veterinary practitioners (pig and poultry sectors), Interprofessional councils (INAPORC for pig and ANVOL for poultry), development institutes (IFIP for pig and ITAVI for poultry)
Italian pigs	Massimo Canali, UNIBO Paolo Trevisi, UNIBO Roberta Ruggeri, UNIBO	Work in progress

	Costanza Romanelli, UNIBO	
Swiss pigs	Barbara Früh, FiBL Bernadette Oehen, FiBL Mirjam Holinger, FiBL	Animal welfare organization, Slaughterhouse / meat production company, Organic farmers association, Veterinary university, Livestock traders, Farmers, Association of Swiss organic pig farmers, Pig health service, Organic research institution, Organic certification body
Swiss veal	Michael Walkenhorst, FiBL Bernadette Oehen, FiBL	Vets, Advisory service (veterinary: Swiss calf health service), organic producer organization (Bio Suisse), veterinary and socio-economic researcher (FiBL), Swiss organic farmers (dairy, beef and veal).
UK calves	Orla Shortall, HUT Claire Hardy, HUT Lee-Ann Sutherland, HUT Carol Kyle, HUT Gareth Enticott, CU Kieran O'Mahony, CU	Farm technicians involved in calf care (Calf-carers / rearers). In addition, based on the development in the LL, a wider group of stakeholders will be invited e.g. consultancies, milk buyers, milk companies, Woman in Dairy-group.

At living labs stakeholders were purposively selected based on initial stakeholder mapping through interviews, to fulfill the multistakeholder-approach and be relevant to stakeholders for the purpose and focus of each Living Lab. In the Deliverable report 4.1 we provided the guidelines as given below. The Living Labs always have the possibility to involve and include new stakeholders, when the need is identified.

When inviting stakeholders to participate in Living Labs, it has been and still is a challenge for some teams to deal with competing companies, and the choice had to be made to cover and focus on the problem area of the ROADMAP project, and the context has been evaluated and taken into account. However, many stakeholders have also potentially conflicting interests in relation to development of the farming sector involving animals (e.g. conflicts between low prices for animal products versus animal welfare concerns), and we consider it a potentially important function of the Living Lab to facilitate processes that bring stakeholders together and can change conflicts of interest to commonalities of interest, when it comes to overall societal concerns, such as antimicrobial resistance, through facilitation and dialogues in the Living Labs by creating rooms of confidence and confidentiality.

Guidelines given in Deliverable Report 4.1 regarding selection of stakeholders for the Living Labs:

It is absolutely fundamental that LLs take a multi-stakeholder approach (Figure 2), and the group of participants or ‘stakeholders’ is heterogeneous and positioned differently in relation to a given issue or problem. Stakeholders may include for example, academics, industry representatives, citizens, public agencies, non-profit organisations, consultants, advisors, entrepreneurs, public authorities, universities, various institutions, end-users, and companies (Almirall and Wareham 2011; Bergvall-Kåreborn et al. 2009; Feurstein et al., 2008; Veeckman et al 2013).

Figure 2. Groups of actors in a LL according to Kris Steen 2017.

Usually, a LL will include public-private-citizen partnership (Dube et al, 2014). The set-up of a LL needs to represent actors who have experience, knowledge and interest in the focus area and the questions of a LL, and who can contribute to co-creation. According to Westerlund and Leminen (2011), there are four main groups of actors who need to be represented in a LL (see Table 2). In other words, it has to be carefully considered who should be invited to participate, both as representatives for certain groups or categories of actors, but also as individuals with personal experience and backgrounds which could be of potential importance for the co-creation process.

In the Living Lab Methodology Handbook (U4LoT, 2019)

it is suggested to consider the following points:

- Participation should be voluntary
- Maximization of diversity among categories of users/actors including public actors (Zavratnik et al, 2019).
- Involve users who are flexible, open for change and have a strong social competence
- Socio-demographic variation in gender, age or education (respective to the context)

During the research process, new stakeholders may be identified that are relevant for inclusion (U4LoT, 2019). On the other hand, stakeholders who do not bring any added value to the living lab should stop their participation (Petruska and Kovacs 2016).

6 CONCLUSION

The guidelines for the selection of individuals to participate in the ROADMAP RSCs have been prepared to ensure best practice for the involvement of stakeholders from across sectors and practice to inform the project’s research and dissemination activities. This project conceived as MAA puts into practice the “interactive innovation model” promoted by EIP-AGRI. It means that knowledge is co-created between scientists and stakeholders. This involves looking at different dimensions, including technical, organizational and social aspects which help’s to bridge the gap between science and practice, applying a “systemic approach”.

This protocol aims to facilitate WPLs (technical contribution) and CLs (regional contribution) within the identification, involvement and engagement of stakeholders clarifying the methodology, roles and activities expected to carry out by each of them. It includes a calendar which show **WHEN** the interactions are taking place, a map **WHERE** which reflects the regions covered by the project, a methodology which explains the **HOW**, a list of key stakeholders desired by ROADMAP on **WHO** chapter and a **WHY** section that cover the main objectives for ROADMAP project.

These activities included in WP7 and led by country leaders will complement to the work planned in WPs 1-6, in which the tasks must be integrated. All the interactions and updates of this guidelines will be measure and reported on a mid-term report on stakeholder's consultation as D7.5 to be developed by FEUGA on M24.

7 REFERENCES

- WINETECH & WINETECH Plus. Innovation Community and new technologies in viticulture and wine-making. Interreg SUDOE 2007-13 www.winetech-sudoe.eu
- AFINET. AgroForestry Innovation Networks. www.agroforestry.eu/afinet
- WINETWORK. Network for the exchange and transfer of innovative knowledge between European wine-growing regions to increase the productivity and sustainability of the sector. www.winetwork.eu
- <https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/about/thematic-networks-%E2%80%93-closing-research-and>
- https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/sites/agri-eip/files/eip-agri_brochure_multi-actor_projects_2017_en_web.pdf

8 ANNEXES

This section includes templates to use in the RSCs creation and organization:

- Annex 1: RSCs Letter of invitation
- Annex 2: RSCs Information Sheet
- Annex 3: Techniques and tools for animate meetings

Letter of invitation
for the Participation in the
REGIONAL STAKEHOLDER COMMUNITY (RSC)
OF NAME OF THE REGION

Dear “ADD TITLE and NAME”

Thank for your interest in the [ROADMAP](#) project (Rethinking of Antimicrobial Decision-systems in the Management of Animal Production) coordinated by INRA. Thank you also for your interest in contributing to the project as a member of our Community.

ROADMAP?

The project ‘[ROADMAP](#)’ was launched Since June 2019. [ROADMAP](#) is a multi-actor approach project which would create Regional Stakeholders Communities (RSCs) for sharing knowledge and experience on prudent antimicrobial use (AMU) in animal production in a large version of contexts, within a European context. Seventeen partners from nine European countries work together in this project and want to give farmers the opportunity to exchange questions, ideas and experiences across the borders. This will be done mainly by organizing regional meetings for practitioners of agro-food, complemented by experts from various fields and other stakeholders, depending on the focus of the networking events.

A work-group on agri-food: what, who, why and how?

Also in “name region” there will be set up such a working group for agro-food (RSC). As mentioned earlier this will meeting is mainly meant for practitioners of agriculture or people having concrete plans to start with agriculture. Depending on the focus of this “Roadmap Stakeholders Community” also researchers, policy makers or suppliers /(potential) buyers of agro-food products can be involved. Crucial for the proper functioning of the RSC is that we can count on committed and motivated participants, but also that it has a direct benefit to all stakeholders concerned. The starting point will therefore always have to respond to specific needs in the field.

What can we offer participants:

- Participation in a motivated multidisciplinary team of experts to assist you in identifying problems, opportunities and solutions.
- Defining the content of the project by signaling where knowledge gaps and problems are currently situated and have a say in how they should be dealt with.
- Having the chance of learning from experts in specific fields. Depending on the issues identified, persons will be sought having the right expertise to share their knowledge with you.
- You broaden your view through following from the first row the knowledge and experiences regarding agri-food practices in Europe.

What is expected of the participants:

- You will participate in the working group meetings.
- You have an active attitude in the RSC meetings. You're transparent about your business, ideas and experiences, think actively in the working group meetings and take part in the discussions.

This group will meet on a frequent basis, a total of at least five times over the course of three years. Both the number of meetings, the location and the agenda will be largely determined by the participants themselves. The interaction will be, however, not restricted to these five official meetings, but we seek a dynamic 'working group' who will also be actively involved in the meantime and according to the needs within the group, exchange information and actively think about and give shape to the project.

“Content? To cover for Case studies”

Practical?

The first meeting will probably take place between late “set date”. As already mentioned, we want to take full account of your wishes. That's why we want to ask your opinion at the latest by “set date”. Please express your interest for participating in the RSC and indicate one or more topics in which you are interested, together with any specific questions or wishes.

Use the link below: “copy link”

Any questions? Contact us.

“Name Surname – email@email.com - Tel. Number”

“Name Surname – email@email.com - Tel. Number”

I am looking forward to hearing from you.

Yours sincerely,

Nicolás Fortané,

(Project Coordinator)

REGIONAL STAKEHOLDER COMMUNITY (RSC) OF NAME OF THE REGION

ROADMAP?

The project ‘ROADMAP’ was launched since June 2019. ROADMAP is a multi-actor approach project which would create Regional Stakeholders Communities (RSCs) for sharing knowledge and experience on prudent antimicrobial use (AMU) in animal production in a large version of contexts, within a European context. Seventeen partners from nine European countries work together in this project and want to give farmers the opportunity to exchange questions, ideas and experiences across the borders. This will be done mainly by organizing regional meetings for practitioners of agro-food, complemented by experts from various fields and other stakeholders, depending on the focus of the networking events.

RSC roles

- **Work Package leaders (WPLs):** They will provide the technical contribution to the project, and participate in the RSCs of their regions, helping Country leaders to select and supervise the activities carry out by Country Leaders.
- **Country Leaders (CLs):** country leaders will identify and engage with stakeholders with the support of WPs 1-6 leaders. They will organize workshops/roundtables (additional to those planned in WPs 1-6) with the intention of covering potential gaps (for instance in terms of stakeholders profiles not sufficiently covered, knowledge gaps, and mainly regions not covered). These activities included in WP7 and led by country leaders will complement to the work planned in WPs 1-6, in which the tasks must be integrated. They will provide the geographical contribution to the project. The CLs may involve some other members of the project in the RSCs when relevant.
- **Stakeholders.** They will guarantee the link with the large community of end-users. Following the instruction of the CLs, they will propose ideas, share their knowledge and experiences in order to develop the activities of the community and to achieve its objectives.

	CATEGORY	DESCRIPTION
1.	Practitioners (animal health professionals):	people who are expected to implement the solutions proposed in field: farmers, veterinarians, technical advisors and farmer’s organizations.
2.	Private partners:	small and medium enterprises (SME’s) linked to the activity, like breeding and feeding industries, pharmaceutical companies, retailers and processors.
3.	Multipliers:	sector and professional associations, NGO’s, EIP-AGRI operational groups from the specific country, regional or national agricultural project partners and networks and other public or private initiatives relevant for the agricultural sector.

4.	Researchers:	researcher groups from universities or technological centres which offer knowledge about agricultural. They have to be able to share their experience and knowledge within the RSCs.
5.	Policy-makers and administration:	public authorities from different policy areas who can foster new politics, regulations or means to empower the sector.

The next figure shows the methodology on the selection and composition of each RSC.

Techniques and tools for animate meetings

Plan meetings: making a meeting more effective with the Three P Statements.

The Three P Statements productivity technique explains the focus, methodology, and value of a meeting. It informs the meeting group of what to expect and what will be accomplished from the start. This technique is used to help a meeting group adequately prepare for the meeting itself. Three P is an acronym of sorts that translates into purpose, process, and payoff, and the technique involves answering three basic and critical questions in statement form: What will we do? How will we do it? Why is it important?

- **Purpose** states what you plan to accomplish. Stating this intention or purpose answers some fundamental questions. Why are we here? What is the goal? Why this meeting is necessary?

A clearly defined purpose for the meeting is essential. Purpose is not a topic or a subject; it's a clear description of the desired outcome of the meeting. It's a goal that everyone is driving towards. Purpose is often, but not always, a decision. But purpose could be brainstorming (to generate the innovation list, e.g.), or gathering information (to get information about bottlenecks, challenges and knowledge gaps in real practice, e.g.).

- **Process** describes how the meeting will address the topic under consideration and answers additional important questions. How will we proceed? What techniques will we use? What steps will we take? How long will this last? What is expected of me? What is expected of the group?
- **Product** informs the participants of the benefit/product, or what they will get from the discussion, and resolves the following questions. Why bother? What is in it for me to participate? What are the real benefits? How will this affect our group's goals?

Not only does the Three P Statements technique provide essential information to the meeting group, it also provides the Innovation Broker as facilitator of the meeting, with critical planning information. If the facilitator of the meeting can't identify the purpose, process, and payoff for any given topic of discussion, does not proceed. If he does, the likelihood of failure will be high.

The Agenda for events, meetings

Creating an effective agenda is one of the most important elements for a productive meeting. The main steps to follow are:

1. Give the agenda a title.
2. Include "who?", "where?", and "when?" information in the header.
3. Write a brief statement of the meeting objective(s).
4. Write a schedule outlining the main elements of the meeting.

5. Leave extra time at the end of the meeting for Q&A.
6. Check the agenda for errors before distributing it.

Facilitation Tools for Meetings and Workshops

Brainstorming: it is a tool for generating ideas for a group of people around a specific area of interest. Using rules which remove inhibitions, people are able to think more freely and move into new areas of thought and so create numerous new ideas and solutions. The participants shout out ideas as they occur to them and then build on the ideas raised by others. All the ideas are noted down and are not criticized. Only when the brainstorming session is over the ideas are evaluated.

Gallery walk: it is a discussion technique that gets people out of their chairs and actively involves them in synthesizing important concepts, in consensus building, in writing, and in public speaking. The facilitator of the meeting prepares several discussion questions and groups people in teams. Questions are posted on different "stations" on room walls, placed on pieces of paper on desks in different locations around room. At each posted question a team reviews what previous groups have written and adds new content. After a short period of time (three to five minutes), the facilitator asks for rotation. The group then rotates, clockwise, to the next station. The rotation continues until all posted questions are addressed. The facilitator can circulate around the classroom, clarifying questions, gauging student understanding, and addressing misconceptions.

When the group returns to the station where it started, the group synthesizes comments and makes an oral report to the room. This stage of the Gallery Walk is a great chance for involving the entire people in discussion and to address misconceptions.

Post-Up. It is an innovation game aimed to generate ideas with silent sticky note writing. There are many ways to work with ideas using sticky notes. Generating ideas is the most basic play, and it starts with a question that the group will be brainstorming answers to. Facilitator writes the question or topic on a whiteboard. He asks the group to brainstorm answers individually, silently writing their ideas on separate sticky notes. The silence lets people think without interruption, and putting items on separate notes ensures that they can later be shuffled and sorted as distinct thoughts. After a set amount of time, facilitator asks the members of the group to stick their notes to the whiteboard and quickly present them. If anyone's items inspire others to write more, they can stick those up on the wall too, after everyone has presented.

Affinity Map. This technique can be used when the facilitator wants to find categories and meta-categories within a cluster of ideas and when he wants to see which ideas are most common within the group. This technique can be conducted only when the facilitator has a question for the players that he knows will generate at least 20 pieces of information to sort. On a sheet of flip-chart paper, he writes a question that the players will respond to along with a visual that complements it. He asks each player to take 10 minutes to generate sticky notes in response to the question. This part of the process has to be conducted silently. The facilitator collects the ideas from the group and posts them on a flat working surface visible to everyone.

Figure 1. Generation process of sticky notes

Based on guidance from the players, the facilitator sorts the ideas into columns (or clusters) based on the relationships. He has to involve the group in the process as much as possible. A good option can be to create a sticky-note “parking lot” close to the display for ideas that don’t appear to fall into a natural category. Redundancy in ideas is OK; it is better doesn’t discard sticky notes because they’re already represented. It’s helpful to leave repeated ideas posted since it indicates to the group how many people are thinking the same thing. At this stage, the facilitator asks the players to try to avoid searching for higher categories and simply to focus on grouping the information based on the affinities. Once the content is sorted, he asks the group to suggest categories that represent the columns that he has created and write the categories they agree on at the top of the column (or near a cluster if you chose a cluster rather than a column display). The facilitator doesn’t let the players spend an inordinate amount of time agreeing on a name for a category. If the players produce categories that are significantly different, he pays attention to which category gets the most approval from the group and write that one. The visual may end up looking like the figure 2.

Figure 2. Final figure of the Affinity Map

Voting techniques.

Multi-Voting Math (or N/3): it is a technique used by small groups to quickly select a subset from a broader set of options. This democratic approach allows team member to cast a finite number of votes, with few restrictions (e.g., individuals can’t “plump” all of their votes on one single candidate), for their options of choice. Ultimately, the process yields a rank order. Some options, the ones with zero or few(er) votes are de-selected, so that the team’s attention can be focused on the surviving options. Multi-voting can be done iteratively to further winnow down the options.

V= N/3

Where:

V= the number of votes allocated to each team member

N= the number of options that are candidates to receive votes

Recall that ceiling brackets require rounding up to the nearest integer.

Multiple Votes and Voting Rounds: it is a democracy system in which people are given multiple votes and the possible decisions with the highest scoring options go on to the next round in which fewer options are given. This group decision process is helpful in that participants are not restricted to one vote. Additionally, by using multiple rounds, participants can make decisions relative to options still available.

More information:

Books:

- Innovation Games®: Creating Breakthrough Products Through Collaborative Play. Author: Luke Hohmann.
- GameStorming: A Playbook for Innovators, Rulebreakers, and Changemakers. Authors: Dave Gray, Sunni Brown and James Macanuffo.

Websites:

- Why you need the 3 P's in every meeting - or don't bother having one: <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/why-you-need-3-ps-every-meeting-dont-bother-having-one-cow-man>
- How to write an agenda for a meeting: <http://www.wikihow.com/Write-an-Agenda-for-a-Meeting>
- Facilitation Tools for Meetings and Workshops. Seeds for Change: www.seedsforchange.org.uk
- 10 Games to foster innovation on your team: <http://www.polleverywhere.com/blog/10-games-to-foster-innovation-on-your-team/>
- Five Useful Methods for Group Decision Making: <http://meetingsift.com/5-useful-methods-for-group-decision-making/>